

**Synthesis of some Fused Heterocyclic
dazoquinolinediones and their
Biological Activity**

AMAL S. YANNI

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science,
Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt

Manuscript received 11 July 1991, accepted 3 September 1991

THE well-known antibiotic antitumor streptonigrin contains the quinoline-5,8-dione system¹. Benzimidazoles have been used as anthelmintics and

antiobesity². Thiazolobenzimidazole derivatives exhibit various biological properties³. With this aspect the title compounds were prepared for biological testing.

In the present study interaction of 6-chloroquinoline-5,8-dione hydrochloride^{4,5} (1) with heterocyclic amines (2-aminopyridine, 5-amino-3-phenylpyrazole, 2-amino-1,3,4-triazole, 2-aminothiazole, 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-aminobenzthiazole and 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole) in pyridine or in ethanol using excess amine gave the cyclised compounds pyrido[1',2':1,2]imidazo[5,4-g]quinoline-5,12-dione (3), 2-phenylpyrazolo[5',1':2,3]imidazo[4,5-g]quinoline-5,10-dione (4), triazolo[2',1':2,3]imidazo[4,5-g]quinoline-5,10-dione (5), thiazolo[3',2':1,2]imidazo[5,4-g]quinoline-5,10-dione (6a, b), benzthiazolo[3',2':1,2]imidazo[5,4-g]quinoline-5,13-dione (7) and thiadiazolo[3',2':1,2]imidazo[5,4-g]quinoline-5,10-dione (8), respectively. These new synthesised compounds are coloured dark brown, show high melting points (>360°) and are sparingly soluble in most organic solvents.

The compounds contains no halogen. Their ir spectra showed absorptions at 3 350–3 400 (NH for 3, 4 only), 1 670–1 650 (C=O of quinone) and 1 590–1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The nmr spectra (TFA) of compounds 6a and 8 revealed signals at δ 7.6–8.85 (5H, m, ArH) and 8.15–8.9 (4H, m, ArH). Mass spectrum (70 eV) of 4 gave M-1 peak at m/z 313. The reaction was suggested to proceed through formation of the quinone free base under the basic condition followed by 1,4-nucleophilic addition⁴ of the heterocyclic amine giving 2 which cyclised under the reaction condition to 3 (Scheme 1).

Biological testing of these compounds (3–8) against *Candida albicans* fungus, and some bacterial species such as *Bacillus cereus*, *Micrococcus roseus*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* showed that 4–8 possess no activity against the tested organisms, while 3 showed remarkable activity against *Bacillus cereus*.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (CF₃CO₂H) on a Varian instrument (90 MHz) and mass spectra on a Varian MAT-311 (70 eV) instrument.

Heterocycloimidazoquinolinediones (3–8): A solution of 1 (0.002 mol) and the appropriate heterocyclic amine (0.002 mol) was refluxed in pyridine (30 ml) for ~25–30 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with dilute acetic acid and alcohol and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as fine brown crystals (50–87%) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (3–8)*

Compd. no.	Yield %	Mol. formula
3	50	C ₁₄ H ₇ N ₂ O ₄
4	72	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂
5	80	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂
6a	87	C ₁₅ H ₈ N ₄ O ₂ S
6b	58	C ₁₈ H ₈ N ₄ O ₂ S
7	68	C ₁₈ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ S
8	60	C ₁₁ H ₄ N ₄ O ₂ S

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses, and 6–8 gave satisfactory S analysis also; m.p.s. of all compounds >360°.

Antimicrobial activity of compounds 3–8: The antimicrobial activity of (3–8) was determined by the usual disc assay method against the above mentioned organisms. The culture medium used was normal nutrient agar containing 1 g of yeast per litre. The bacterial and fungal suspensions were prepared by adding sterile distilled water (1 ml) to a 48 h old culture of the test organism grown on nutrient agar slant.

References

1. T. K. LIAO, W. H. NYBERG and C. C. CHENG, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1967, 6, 82.
2. P. N. PETERSON, *Chem. Rev.*, 1974; 74, 279; HOULIHAN, WILLIAM and JOSEPH, S. Afr. Pat. 78 05 778/1978.
3. V. K. CHADHA, H. S. CHAUDHARY and H. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 769; K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and P. ARYA, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1977, 41, 543; H. S. CHAUDHARY, C. S. PANDA and H. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 10; J. MOHAN, V. K. CHADHA, H. S. CHAUDHARY, B. D. SHARMA, H. K. PUJARI and L. N. MOHAPATRA, *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1972, 10, 37; H. J. SHOLL, E. KLAUKE, P. CREWE and I. HAMMANN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1972, 77, 114391; J. J. D'AMICO, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1966, 64, 8193; G. HASEGAWA and A. KOTANI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, 82, 156299.

NOTES

4. Y. T. PRATT, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 3905.
5. A. M. OSMAN, A. S. HAMMAM, Z. H. KHALIL and
A. S. YANNI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**,
325.